

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

“AN INTERVENTIONAL STUDY ON KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE & PRACTICE TOWARDS URINARY TRACT INFECTION AMONG ADOLESCENT GIRLS STUDENTS IN SELECTED GIRLS SCHOOLS IN CHITRADURGA CITY”

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 07/04/2017

Available online

31/01/2018

Keywords

Adolescent,
Interventional study,
Urinary Tract Infection.

ABSTRACT

Background: Urinary tract infection (UTI) is a bacterial infection found to be more prevalent among the adolescent girls than any other age groups. Therefore, a good promotional dissemination on UTI is important to convey accurate information to the society. Objectives of the study were to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices (KAP) towards UTI among adolescent girl students and to assess the impact of structured education by means of self-designed questionnaire. Methods: A community based interventional study was carried out among the students in selected girl's schools in Chitradurga city for a period of six months. Paired t-test was used to detect the association status of different variables. Results: The results implicated that out of 467 adolescent girls enrolled in the study, mean score regarding the knowledge on UTI in pre-test $4.78(\pm 1.6)$ had increased to $10.87(\pm 1.301)$ in post-test after intervention. Also 10th grade students ($4.94(\pm 1.89)$) had higher level of knowledge than other grades. It was also observed that majority of the students were following unhealthy practices like drying the clothes under fan (21.17%), keeping the same napkin for long hours (76.75%), improper perineal washing (97.29%), lack of menstrual hygienity, use of unsanitary napkins (5.99%) etc. After intervention they started following hygienic practices. Conclusion: The study has shown a prompt result in improving the knowledge through KAP. This signifies the need and importance of implementing various teaching programs for adolescent girls on various topics as it would help to improve knowledge and follow healthy practices to build a healthy nation.

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Please cite this article in press as **Anjaly Vijayan et al.** “An Interventional Study on Knowledge, Attitude & Practice Towards Urinary Tract Infection Among Adolescent Girls Students In Selected Girls Schools in Chitradurga City”. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(01).

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INTRODUCTION

UTI is a bacterial infection that affects part of the urinary tract and is caused by microorganisms such as E.coli, Staphylococcus aureus, Klebsiella pneumonia etc. The most common cause for the infection is unhygienic bathrooms where the microorganisms are found. It affects the urinary tract that comprises of urethra, urinary bladder, ureter and kidneys. Lower UTI is known as a simple cystitis and when it affects kidneys it is known as pyelonephritis. E.coli is the cause of 80–85% of UTIs and Staphylococcus being the cause in 5–10%. Signs and symptoms of UTI includes fever, chills, dysuria, supra pubic pressure or discomfort, flank pain, urination or urge to urinate etc. The chances of women suffering from UTI are 50% more than men, because the sources of bacterial infection like the vagina and anus are positioned close to the urinary opening leading to its higher prevalence in females. Acute uncomplicated UTI is more prevalent among adolescent girls and found to be the fourth main reason for outpatient visit among this group. It is estimated that 150 million UTIs occur yearly on a global basis, resulting in more than six billion dollars in direct health care expenditures. Hence the objective of the study was to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices on UTI among adolescent girls students and improve knowledge on the different aspects of UTI among adolescent girl students. Health education programs play a major role in creating awareness and improving the knowledge regarding various bacterial infections particularly UTI and also ensure that this knowledge gets translated into practice as well to build up a healthy nation.

METHODOLOGY

A community based interventional study was used to assess knowledge attitude and practices towards UTI among selected girl's schools of Chitradurga city with the prior approval from the School head master and Institution Ethical committee. The study was conducted in two selected girls schools of Chitradurga city i.e. Government Girls Junior College, Chitradurga (English medium) (GGJC) and Priyadharshini Girls High School, Chitradurga Kannada medium) (PGHS) The study was carried out for a period of six months. The target population was students from 8th, 9th and 10th classes of selected schools. A total of 467 students were selected out of which, 359 were from English medium and 108 were from Kannada medium school. Baseline knowledge of the students regarding UTI was obtained by means of self-designed questionnaires. After baseline assessment the students were educated regarding UTI by means of power point presentations and lectures (both in Kannada and English). The first follow up was made after one month in which the knowledge of students was reassessed by means of above mentioned questionnaires. The questionnaire was of closed end type. Each correct answer was given a score of one and wrong answer given a score of zero. Then from the differences in the scores of the pre-test and post-test, the impact of the study was analyzed by means of paired t-test.

RESULT:

Among the total study population (n=467) who participated in the study, 359(76.9%), 108(23.1%) students belongs to Govt. Girls Junior College (GGJC) and Priyadharshini Girls Higher Secondary School (PGHS) respectively. After intervention mean score of the students in pre-test 4.78 has increase to 10.8 in post-test (Figure: 1).

Figure:1 distribution of mean score.

During the study, in pre-test it was observed that 10th class student had better knowledge of on UTI than other standards as it was included in their academics. After intervention in post-test the mean score of 8th, 9th, 10th classes has increased (Figure: 2).

Figure:2 Standard wise distribution of scores.

Medium wise mean score in pre-test shows that English medium students of mean score (4.87 (\pm 1.61)) has more knowledge on UTI than Kannada medium students (4.45 (\pm 1.51)) (Figure: 3).

Figure: 3 Medium Wise Distributions of Scores.

During the study it was observed that majority of students were following wrong practices of drying undergarments, like under fan, shade etc that can cause them UTI. During intervention the students were educated about the need of drying undergarments under direct sunlight and started to dry under direct sunlight (Table:1).

Table:1 Response for method of Drying Under garments.

SL.NO	Response	Pre-Test	Post-Test
1	Under direct sunlight	182	431
2	In Shade	196	27
3	Under Fan	102	9
	Total	480	467

Also, during pre-test it was observed that majority of students were following improper method of perineal washing. But after educational campaign the students started following proper method that is, from Urethra to Anus (Up to Down) that can be seen from post-test response. (Table: 2).

Table: 2 Response for method of Perineal Washing.

Sl.No	Response	Pre-Test	Post-Test
1	From Anus To Urethra (Down To Up)	89	18
2	Urethra To Anus (Up To Down)	13	431
3	Both Ways	378	18
	Total	480	467

During the pre-test it has been found that majority of the students were unhygienic during menstruation such as keeping napkins for long hours (>6 hrs). But after educational campaign students started following healthy practices which is evident from the post-test response. (Figure: 4).

Figure: 4 Response for Duration of Keeping a Napkin during Menstruation.

During the study it was found that some of the students were using un sanitary napkins (cloths). After intervention everyone started using sanitary napkins which is healthy. (Table: 3).

Table: 3 Responses for Type of Napkin Using During Menstruation.

Sl.No	Response	Pre-Test	Post-Test
1	Home Made Napkins(Cloth)	28	3
2	Sanitary Napkins	452	464
	Total	480	467

DISCUSSION

Adolescent girls (12-16years) were chosen for the study as UTI is more prevalent in adolescent girls and young females than in males and with an intention to prevent UTI among them through health education. In India, the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) 2000 reported the prevalence of UTI among adolescent girls (10-19 years) as 16.6% and the risk of bacteraemia developing in adolescent girls as 5-10%. The study aimed to create awareness on the different aspects of UTI among adolescent girls (12-16 years) and thus to improve their knowledge on the same by means of the social vaccine, KAP. This study was carried out among the high school students of selected girl's schools in Chitradurga city. A significant change in the level of knowledge, attitude and practices on UTI among the study subjects has been observed, which is evident from increase in mean score during post-test Mean (\pm SD)=4.78(\pm 1.6) from pre-test score Mean (\pm SD)=10.8(\pm 1.301). A total of 467 students from selected girls schools who had satisfied the study criteria were enrolled, students from standard X (Mean (\pm SD)=4.94 (\pm 1.89) had better knowledge than others that is VIII and IX standard as they have learned about UTI in their academics. But however the knowledge on UTI among students was average. This study also revealed strong association between UTI and improper perineal washing technique, use of unsanitary pads during menstruation, long hours of keeping napkins, improper drying of undergarments, and unhygienic practices during menstruation. Similar results were revealed by other south Indian studies by Singh M M and Narayan BK. Similarly, Indhumol T D *et al.*, have reported that knowledge of the students on UTI were average and that the main contributing factors for UTI are inadequate poor voiding habits, unhygienic practices during menstruation, inadequate personal hygiene and toilet habits.

As per Ahmed SM *et al.*, Overall prevalence of UTI among adolescent girls is 12.7% i.e. 23 girls and states that there was a significant association between prevalence of UTI and improper perineal washing technique, and use of unsanitary pads during menses, frequent use of same piece of cloth or sanitary pads during menstrual bleeding leading to UTI.

CONCLUSION

After the study it was concluded that majority of the students who had participated in the study had average knowledge regarding UTRI in pre test. After the intervention or teaching programme the students has gained good knowledge. This is evident from post-test score in comparison with pre-test scores. This signifies the need and importance of implementing various teaching programs for adolescent students on various topics as it would help to improve knowledge and follow healthy practices in turn improve the quality of life and thus help to build up a healthy nation. Hence health education programs play a major role in creating awareness and to improve the knowledge regarding various bacterial infections particularly UTIs.

REFERENCES

1. Indhumol TD, Pavithran S, George LK. Effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding prevention of Urinary Tract Infection among adolescent girls. International Journal Of Pharma Medicine and Biological sciences.2014;3 (3):122-26.
2. Narayan KA, Shrivastava, DK, Pelto PJ, Veeramal S. Puberty rituals, reproductive and health of adolescent school girls of south India. Asia Pacific Population Journal June, 2001; 16:225-38.
3. Orrett FA. Urinary tract infection in general practice in a rural community in south Trinidad. Saudi Med J.2001; 22(6) 537-40
4. Urinary Tract Infections (UTIs) From HEALTH TOPICS on the UHS Web site, www.rochester.edu/uhs.

5. The KAP Survey Model(Knowledge, Attitude,Practice)Specifically on knowledg, attitudes and practices:25- 71.
6. Jahanbin I, Heydari N, Ghodsbin F, Sayadi M. The effect of peer-education on UTI-related preventive behavior according to HBM among first-grade high school female students in Shiraz.J.Health Sci surveillance sys.2015;3(3):20-26.
7. Ogomaka IA, Ndudim D, Ogbulie, DikeTE, Nwokeji R, Egbuobi RC.Urinary tract infection among teenagers in Umudioka in Orulga of imostate,Nigeria. Scientific Research Journal.2014;2(1): 25-28.
8. Margaret G. Pelvic I Balamurugan SS, Shilpa SS, Shaji S. A Community Based Study On Menstrual Hygiene Among Reproductive Age Group Women In A Rural Area, Tamil Nadu. journal Of Basic And Clinical Reproductive Sciences.2014;3(2):83-87.
9. Yasmin S, Manna N, Mallik S, Ahmed A, Paria B. Menstrual hygiene among adolescent school students: An in-depth cross-sectional study in an urban community of West Bengal, India. IOSR J Dent Med Sci.2013; 5:22:4-10.
10. Onyemelukwe, NF, Nwokocha, Arc.Staphylococcus Saprophyticus Infections as a Cause of UTI In Female Adolescents in Enugu Area, Nigeria. IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences (IOSR-JDMS).2013; 11(5):37-40.
11. Ray S et al.,(2012) Determinants of Menstrual Hygiene among Adolescent Girls: A Multivariate Analysis among 190 adolescent girls of a rural secondary school of West Bengal. IOSR Journal of Medical Science. 2012;4(3):10-18
12. Thakre SB, Thakre SS, Reddy M, Pathak N, Ughade S.Menstrual hygiene knowledge and practice among adolescent school girls of Saoner, Nagpur ditrict.Journal of clinical and diagnostic research.2011;5(5):1027-033.
13. Ahmed SM, Avasarala AK. Urinary tract infections among adolescent girls in rural Karimnagar district, Ap – K.A.P. Study. Indian.J Prev.Soc. Med.2009; 40(1&2):1-9.
14. Aiyegoro OA, Igbinsosa OO, Ogunmwonyi IN, Odjadjare EE, Igbinsosa OE, Okoh AI.Incidence of urinary tract infections (UTI) among children and adolescents in Ile-Ife, Nigeria. African Journal of Microbiology.2007:013-019.
15. NarayanBK. puberty rituals, reproductive knowledge and health of adolescent school girls in south India. Asia Pacific Population Journal.2002;3 (5):23-28.

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